

Sustainable Disposal and End-of-Life Treatment of Battery Energy Storage Systems: An Environmental and Economic Case Study

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Abstract

As global energy systems transition towards decarbonization and increased reliance on renewable resources, battery energy storage systems (BESSs) have become integral to ensuring grid stability and grid-integrating intermittent renewable sources. Yet the BESS widespread adoption is challenged by the significant environmental and economic challenges posed by end-of-life management, particularly for lithium-ion batteries (LIBs). This work presents a detailed environmental and economic evaluation of a case study on the EOL treatment of a 2.8 MWh/2.5 MW BESS. It covers recycling pre-treatment processes for battery systems, recycling procedures for cooling systems, extinguishing systems, inverters, and reuse applications for BESS's container and substation. The study uses a life cycle assessment (LCA) focusing on impacts related to climate change, eutrophication, freshwater, and resource use, minerals and metals. Results reveal significant environmental benefits from recovering secondary materials, particularly aluminium and copper, while highlighting that recycling pre-treatment processes contribute approximately one-third of the overall environmental benefits. Furthermore, the economic analysis identifies potential gains from recycling BESS, projecting profits of around €69,000 per unit, underscoring the importance of local sourcing for critical raw materials. Moreover, this work identifies potential gains from recycling BESSs and highlights benefits like self-sufficiency in critical raw materials production. This study underscores the importance of developing more sustainable recycling practices and offers crucial insights for advancing environmental and economic strategies in BESS management. As such, it provides valuable guidance for future research and policy development to enhance the sustainability of battery waste processing.

Keywords: lithium-ion battery, battery energy storage system, end-of-life, recycling pre-treatment, environmental perspective, economic evaluation

1. Introduction

Energy systems are undergoing a global transformation driven by technological advancements, decarbonization efforts, the deployment of smart grids, and the increasing integration of renewable energy resources. Historically, fossil fuels were critical for power generation, but their use has led to significant greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and global warming. To combat this, the world is shifting toward decarbonization by reducing emissions and expanding sustainable energy sources (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), 2023; IRENA, 2023). This shift to decentralized power generation and the need for autonomous microgrids pose challenges for the infrastructure of the power grids (Nebey, 2024). Battery energy storage systems (BESSs) are crucial in this context by storing and releasing energy to ensure stable and reliable operation of the power grids. BESSs are used for load leveling, grid frequency regulation, and backup power during outages. Furthermore, they are especially

valuable for the grid integration of intermittent and not 100% predictable renewable energy sources like solar and wind, ensuring a consistent power supply (IRENA, 2017; Zakeri & Syri, 2015). They also defer costly infrastructure upgrades by reducing the need for peaking power plants and minimizing transmission and distribution enhancements (Divya & Østergaard, 2009; Hannan et al., 2021). However, challenges include high installation costs, limited battery lifespan, and negative environmental impacts from battery disposal. Battery performance degradation over time raises scalability concerns for large-scale storage. Despite these issues, BESSs are increasingly considered for renewable energy grid-integration and grid support. As technology advances and costs decline, BESSs are essential for a sustainable energy future (Hannan et al., 2021; Hengky K. Salim et al., 2019). Considering the ever-increasing share of these systems within the infrastructure, evaluating their end-of-life (EOL) treatment is a crucial research field (Toro et al., 2023).

Waste treatment of BESSs is crucial for sustainable management, as it facilitates resource recovery, reduces environmental impacts, and supports the transition to a circular economy (Pinto et al., 2024; Sulemanu, 2023). These systems typically operate for 10 to 20 years, similar to the maximum 10-year lifespan of EV batteries (Ohrelius et al., 2023). Given their similar technology, there is interest in repurposing EOL modules from EVs for BESS installations, extending battery life and enhancing resource efficiency. Efficient recycling and recovery processes for BESS components allow for extracting valuable materials and reducing the environmental footprint (Larcher & Tarascon, 2015; Sulemanu, 2023). Currently, BESSs used in both small-scale and large industrial systems, are mostly based on the lithium-ion battery (LIB) technology (Hannan et al., 2021; Ohrelius et al., 2023). The high proportion of rare materials like cobalt, nickel, manganese, and lithium in these batteries underscores the importance of efficient EOL management to maximize resource utilization and sustainability (Conzen et al., 2023).

These battery cells consist of active layers made from materials such as lithium cobalt oxide (LiCoO_2), lithium iron phosphate (LiFePO_4), nickel cobalt aluminium (NCA), or nickel manganese cobalt oxide (NMC) deposited on aluminium foils, which serve as the current collectors for the positive electrodes. The negative electrodes typically comprise a graphite layer deposited on copper current collectors. Additionally, the electrolyte typically contains lithium hexafluorophosphate (LiPF_6) salt dissolved in organic solvents, which enables the movement of lithium ions through polymer separators between the electrodes during charging and discharging cycles (Pražanová et al., 2022a; Thompson et al., 2020; Zhu et al., 2021).

Individual battery cells are combined into modules, which act as the fundamental building blocks of BESSs. These modules arrange cells in series and parallel to meet the desired voltage, capacity, and performance. In BESS installations, modules are arranged in arrays, interconnected with power electronics and control systems for managing charging, discharging, and overall operation (Chang et al., 2018; Ovaskainen et al., 2023). This modular design facilitates scalability and flexibility, allowing for the creation of BESSs tailored to various energy storage needs, whether for small-scale residential applications or large-scale industrial deployments supporting grid stability and renewable energy integration (Conzen et al., 2023; IRENA, 2023; Pinto et al., 2024). However, it is crucial to note that despite the advancements in materials over the past three decades, the fundamental design of these battery cells has largely remained unchanged. This poses significant challenges for recycling, as the current design does not prioritize recyclability, thereby limiting the long-term sustainability of battery systems. Addressing these challenges is essential for ensuring that future battery technologies are both effective in energy storage and environmentally responsible.

In addition to battery modules, BESSs consist of several other essential components, such as power converters to manage power flow and interface with the power grid, thermal

management systems (TMS), which are crucial for maintaining optimal operating temperatures within the batteries to ensure efficiency and longevity, fire extinguishing system, which is used in case of emergencies, and energy management systems (EMS) will monitor and control the charging, discharging, and overall performance of the BESS. The enclosure or container also provides structural support and protection for the system. From a material composition perspective, inverters are typically based on steel and copper, including capacitors (often aluminium electrolytic or ceramic) and copper-based inductors, and printed circuit boards (PCBs) containing copper or traces of gold. The TMS incorporates heat sinks, heat pipes, insulation materials like ceramics or polymers, and pressure cylinders with fire suppression elements, typically nitrogen based. The EMS integrates microcontrollers, sensors, and semiconductors within its circuitry. The container is generally constructed from steel, aluminium, or composites. In some installations, a substation composed of steel, aluminium, and composites may also be considered part of the BESS (Chang et al., 2018; Hossain et al., 2019; Jasper et al., 2022; H. K. Salim et al., 2020).

Battery systems pose complex challenges in waste processing compared to other components, often processed through metal recovery or repair. Handling batteries involves several steps: disassembling modules from racks, deep discharging to prevent ignition, and crushing to separate materials like current collectors, active electrode materials, and packaging. Thermal treatment removes organic components such as electrolytes and binders. The output, known as black mass (a valuable mix of metals) can be traded and is central to efficient recycling. Black mass is then processed through pyrometallurgy, which uses high temperatures to recover metals, or hydrometallurgy, which employs chemical solutions. These methods recover valuable elements like lithium, cobalt, nickel, and manganese, which can be reused in battery manufacturing, supporting sustainability. Thus, efficient pre-treatment is essential for producing black mass consistently and effectively. (Chang et al., 2018; Hossain et al., 2019; Li Li et al., 2018; Liu et al., 2022; Anna Pražanová et al., 2022a; Toro et al., 2023).

Nevertheless, the EOL treatment of LIBs presents several significant challenges that must be addressed. Recycling and pre-treatment methods are energy-intensive and financially highly demanding (Li et al., 2018). A key research gap exists in the standardization of recycling methodologies, as current studies often do not account for the variability in recycling operations and their efficiency. Additionally, not all technologies can achieve 100% recovery of materials or may result in high volumes of waste or the production of hazardous by-products (Hayes & McCullough, 2018). Another gap lies in understanding the cumulative environmental impacts of these pre-treatment processes, particularly the energy consumption and emissions generated. The diversity of individual recycling operations further complicates the process. Each step in the recycling chain, from disassembly to the final recovery of materials, can vary significantly in efficiency and environmental impacts. Therefore, it is not feasible to generalize broadly about the effectiveness of LIB recycling technologies (Chen et al., 2019; Hayes & McCullough, 2018; Natarajan & Aravindan, 2018; Sommerville et al., 2021). Instead, each process must be evaluated individually, considering the specific steps and methods used. The present work addresses these gaps by assessing the environmental and economic viability of EOL treatment processes through a new case study. It expands existing research, highlighting the importance of evaluating each process individually.

The environmental impacts of EOL treatment for LIB-based BESSs are significant, particularly in recycling pre-treatment. While these processes simplify recycling and mitigate environmental footprints, they pose challenges. The energy-intensive nature of pre-treatment steps increases the carbon footprint, requiring careful management. Studies like Romare & Dahllöf (2017) indicate that energy consumption during disassembly and discharge significantly impacts the environmental performance of battery recycling. Crushing and material separation also increase the environmental burden, generating dust and hazardous

emissions. Despite the advancements in recycling, a significant gap remains in optimizing these pre-treatment processes to minimize their environmental impact while maintaining high recovery rates. These processes isolate valuable components using mechanical, chemical, or thermal methods but produce secondary waste and emissions. Bobba et al. (2018) note that pre-treatment processes contribute significantly to the environmental impacts, with high-energy machinery and chemical treatments causing considerable GHG emissions and resource consumption. Despite these challenges, effective recycling pre-treatment recovers valuable materials, reducing the need for virgin materials and associated mining impacts. This study contributes by evaluating the trade-offs between environmental impacts and material recovery efficiency, providing insights into the environmental implications of these processes.

The economic aspects of recycling are complex. Due to the specialized handling required, high initial costs for disassembly, deep discharge, and processing are significant, as noted by Harper et al. (2019). Energy use in pre-treatment, such as crushing and separation, increases operational expenses. Current research often overlooks the long-term economic implications of fluctuating market prices for recovered materials and the high costs associated with specialized handling. Fluctuating market prices for recovered materials like lithium, cobalt, and nickel also impact profitability, as highlighted by Larcher & Tarascon (2015). This study provides a comprehensive economic analysis that includes these fluctuations and evaluates the potential for cost recovery through effective recycling. However, effective recycling can recover valuable materials, potentially offsetting costs. Wang et al. (2014) emphasize that efficient processes yield high-purity materials for new batteries, reducing the need for raw material mining and stabilizing supply. Advancements in technology can decrease costs through economies of scale (Gaines, 2018), and developing recycling infrastructure can generate new jobs and industries. Hayes & McCullough (2018) highlight that a comprehensive battery recycling industry can spur economic growth by generating employment in the recycling sector and related fields, such as transportation and manufacturing of recycling equipment. Thus, this study uniquely leverages the use of a BESS container as the unit of analysis, emphasizing its potential EOL value and providing a framework for investors to consider this value during initial investment decisions.

This study addresses the critical issue of evaluating the environmental and economic impacts of EOL treatment for BESS. Centred on a 2.8 MWh/2.5 MW LIB-based BESS, it examines the recycling pre-treatment of batteries, the treatment of cooling systems, extinguishing systems, and inverters, and reusing containers and substations in new installations. By using a gate-to-gate life cycle assessment (LCA), the study provides new insights into the substantial environmental benefits of reusing secondary materials like aluminium, copper, and steel, quantifying these benefits more comprehensively than previous research. Economically, BESS recycling presents clear benefits, even with the additional costs for supplementary technologies. This study further contributes to the field by highlighting the economic advantages of local raw material production, which reduces import dependency, improves supply chain security, and lowers costs and environmental impacts from transportation. The findings highlight the dual benefits of BESS recycling: significant environmental improvements through material reuse and notable economic gains. Additionally, this study emphasizes that transitioning to renewable energy sources for recycling would further enhance these benefits, supporting broader sustainability objectives and offering a path forward for more sustainable recycling practices.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Goal, scope, and assumptions

This work assesses the environmental and economic impacts of a case study involving a BESS EOL treatment. This system, operated and intended for processing in the conditions of the Czech Republic, is primarily designed to provide frequency regulation services and has a maximum energy storage capacity of 2.8 MWh, representing one of the commonly used capacity sizes for systems installed under the conditions typical in the Czech Republic (IBG Česko s.r.o., 2019; Siemens s.r.o., 2019). Its peak power output of up to 2.5 MW aligns with the standard requirements for providing frequency regulation and grid stability in medium-sized energy storage applications (Prakash et al., 2022).

The considered BESS system consists of six components: the battery system, thermal management (cooling) system, extinguishing system, inverters, the container, and the distribution board. Figure 1(a) illustrates the categorization of these components based on their EOL treatment evaluated in this study. The focus is placed on the battery, thermal management, and extinguishing systems, as well as the inverters, all of which are intended for EOL processing. The treatment of these components primarily involves recycling or secondary-use material recovery. The BESS container and the substation, while expected to have a long lifespan and potential for reuse after minor modifications, revisions, and service, are not part of this assessment as they are beyond the scope of this study, focusing on a later stage of second-life application.

Figure 1. (a) Illustration of the battery energy storage system (BESS) components categorized by their respective treatments considered in the study. (b) Process characterization of the treatment steps for individual components, detailing material and energy flows.

The BESS unit, represented as a single container, consists of 409 LIB modules, which together house a total of 9,816 pouch cells based on NMC chemistry (IBG Česko s.r.o., 2019; A. Pražanová et al., 2022). Designed for waste treatment, the entire battery system weighs 13,088 kg and comprises these 409 modules, each with a weight of 32 kg. Within each module, there are 24 battery cells, weighing 1.1 kg each, along with a cover that adds 4.7 kg and binding materials totalling 0.91 kg. Each battery cell's composition includes approximately 44% positive electrode active materials (based on NMC 6.5:2:1.5), 32% graphite, 6% copper, 7.5% aluminium, 4.5% aluminium-polymer casing, and 6% organic and plastic parts, which encompass the separator, binders, and electrolyte. In this study, "black mass" refers specifically to a product composed solely of positive electrode active materials. Generally, black mass can be understood as a mixture of valuable battery materials (from both electrodes, along with remnants of current collectors or casing materials). Given the nature of the applied method and the ability to directly recover selected materials, the black mass in this work is exclusively composed of NMC-based spinel

The electrical infrastructure includes four transformer-less hybrid inverters rated at 630 kW (Megarevo, 2024; Selvamathi et al., 2018) and one low-voltage distribution board (HIVE Connective Intelligence, 2023). The inverters collectively weigh 3,800 kg and comprise 1,140 kg of iron, 1,520 kg of aluminium, and 1,140 kg of electronic components, making them crucial for efficient energy conversion. Two cooling units with a heat output capacity of 12.5 kW are used to regulate the system's temperature (HIVE Connective Intelligence, 2023). The cooling system weighs a total of 490 kg and consists of 181.3 kg of iron (to be processed as pig iron), 63.7 kg of aluminium, 73.5 kg of copper, 28 kg of brass, 122.5 kg of plastics, 14 kg of electronic elements, and 7 kg of refrigerants. Additionally, fire safety measures, including an extinguishing system, are in place, based on based on four steel pressure cylinders, each weighing 70.2 kg, filled with 23.4 kg of nitrogen gas to ensure proper gas distribution for fire suppression (Global, 2017). All these components are housed in a metal shipping container with suitable accessories to support the system's operation and safety (HIVE Connective Intelligence, 2023). The weights of the processed materials for the individual components of the entire BESS are shown in Table 1. Considering an optimistic scenario and the exceptionally high efficiency of the technology, the input materials also represent the values of the intermediate or resulting materials obtained from the assessed processes.

The dismantling of the BESS begins with the removal of the battery system, where individual modules are manually disassembled from their racks and subsequently transported to the recycling facility. Upon arrival, the modules undergo a discharge process to recover any residual energy, after which the duralumin covers are milled off. The pouch cells, now separated from the cover residue, are subjected to robotic disassembly. During this stage, the electrode sets are sorted into cathodes and anodes, enabling further processing of these materials. The sorted components are then sheared and crushed before being fired in a furnace to enhance material recovery. In this work, it is assumed that all lithium is lost during this process. Following the firing process, current collectors are cleaned using ultrasonic baths, while filtration methods are employed to separate cleaned metal foils from the active materials. Any residual water is removed from the solid residues via centrifugation, after which the materials are dried and prepared for further treatment. Material handling throughout this process is efficiently managed by an electric forklift.

Battery system			Cooling system		Extinguishing system		Inverters	
	Material	Mass (kg)	Material	Mass (kg)	Material	Mass (kg)	Material	Mass (kg)
Module	Duralumin cover	1,922	Iron	181.3	Steel	280.8	Iron	1,140
	Organics (binders, plastics)	372	Aluminium	63.7	Nitrogen	93.64	Aluminium	1,520
Cell	Copper	661	Copper	73.5			Electronics	1,140
	Aluminium	812	Brass	28				
	Positive electrode active materials	4,721	Electronics	14				
	Graphite	3,465	Refrigerator	7				
	Aluminium-polymer casing	491	Plastics	122.5				
	Organics (electrolyte, separator, binders, plastics)	643						
Total mass (kg)		13,088		490		374		3,800

Table 1. The summary of material composition of the evaluated components in the battery energy storage system (BESS) including the battery system, cooling system, fire extinguishing system, and inverters. For the positive electrode active materials based on NMC 6.5:2:1.5, the distribution of elements is as follows: 65% nickel, 15% manganese, and 20% cobalt. The total amounts of these materials within the entire battery system are 3,069 kg of nickel, 944 kg of manganese, and 708 kg of cobalt.

In addition to the battery system, the cooling units are dismantled and transported for waste treatment. The fluorocarbon-based cooling medium is extracted before manually dismantling electronic elements and significant parts. The remaining materials are then crushed and separated, with iron-based components being magnetically extracted and non-ferrous metals sorted electrostatically. Fire extinguishing systems are similarly disassembled using hand tools and transported to the end-of-life treatment plant, where nitrogen and steel bottles are processed and prepared for reuse. The inverters follow the same transportation process, allowing for the extraction of aluminium, pig iron, and electronic scraps. The process characterization of the treatment steps for individual components is illustrated in Figure 1(b), and the detailed information regarding consumption, management, and the use of the selected equipment is provided in the Supplementary materials.

In this study, the baseline scenario was defined with the assumption of maximum yield and processing efficiency for all treated components. This perspective posits that the processes are entirely lossless concerning materials designated for secondary use or further processing. Such an optimistic scenario serves as an idealized framework for evaluating the processes at their highest efficiency, thereby providing valuable insights into the lowest environmental impacts and the maximum potential profits that can be achieved through processing. To enhance the realism of the assessment, Overall Equipment Effectiveness (OEE) was incorporated into the analysis. This adjustment accounts for operational inefficiencies, including micro

downtimes and intermediate processing steps, which often result in machines operating below their total capacity. By integrating OEE, the analysis not only more accurately reflects practical industrial conditions but also offers a comprehensive representation of real-world scenarios, facilitating a deeper understanding of the potential challenges and opportunities within the BESS treatment processes.

2.2 Environmental evaluation

This study conducts a partial gate-to-gate LCA (International Organization for Standardization, 2006) focusing on the EOL treatment of BESS, specifically examining recycling pre-treatment steps. It treats the used LIBs as burden-free, not including the environmental impacts from their previous lifecycle phases. The outputs obtained from this process are intended for further treatment. The assessment was performed using the 9.5 version of the SimaPro LCA modelling software, utilizing the Ecoinvent 3.9 database with a Cut-Off approach and the Environmental Footprint 3.1 (EF 3.1) Impact Assessment method. The scope and life-cycle boundaries of this study within the LIB life cycle are illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3. The scheme of system boundaries, which were considered for this partial LCA study. Study inputs (end-of-life batteries, energy) are shown in blue and outputs (recovered materials) in green.

This study evaluates the EOL treatment of four main BESS components: the LIB system, the cooling system with air-conditioning units, the fire extinguishing system, and the inverters. Each component underwent recycling, with the LIB system primarily producing black mass, a valuable mixture of materials. Significant secondary materials, including metals like aluminium, copper, and graphite, were recovered, highlighting the efficiency of the recycling process. The cooling system produced secondary aluminium, copper, iron, and brass. The fire extinguishing system provided secondary steel, while the inverter yielded secondary iron and aluminium. These materials will be reused, reducing the environmental impact by substituting primary materials. However, some materials were treated as waste in this process. Plastics from the batteries and cooling systems were incinerated. Electronic scrap was separated into steel and cables. The refrigerant from the cooling unit was treated separately, while nitrogen from the fire extinguishing system was released into the atmosphere.

The energy mix employed for operating the recycling machinery was based on the current Czech energy mix – fossil fuels (50.78 %), nuclear energy (42.82 %), renewables (6,4 %) (Czech electricity and gas market operator (OTE a.s.), 2024). Due to varying recycling

methods and battery system compositions, this study quantifies environmental impacts per one recycled BESS container. This functional unit enables clear comparisons between recycling pathways and allows for transparent analysis of each BESS component's contribution to the life cycle. More details of the evaluation using this functional unit in selected ICs are provided in the Supplementary materials of this work. A detailed examination of the Ecoinvent 3.9 processes used for modelling is provided in Table 2.

Ecoinvent 3.9 processes	Description
Avoided products (secondary materials)	
Aluminium, primary, ingot {RoW} aluminium production, primary, ingot Cut-off, U	secondary material
Copper, cathode {GLO} market for copper, cathode Cut-off, U	secondary material
Graphite, battery grade {RoW} graphite production, battery grade Cut-off, U	secondary material
Steel, chromium steel 18/8 {GLO} market for steel, chromium steel 18/8 Cut-off, U	secondary material
Pig iron {RER} pig iron production Cut-off, U	secondary material
Brass {RoW} brass production Cut-off, U	secondary material
Waste products (end-of-life)	
Waste plastic, mixture {RoW} treatment of waste plastic, mixture, municipal incineration Cut-off, U	waste plastic (batteries)
Waste plastic, consumer electronics {RoW} treatment of waste plastic, consumer electronics, municipal incineration Cut-off, U	waste plastic (AC)
Electronics scrap from control units {GLO} market for electronics scrap from control units Cut-off, U	waste electronics (AC, inverter)
Used refrigerant R134a {GLO} treatment of used refrigerant R134a, reclamation Cut-off, U	waste refrigerant
Other (energy, transport)	
Transport, freight, lorry 7.5-16 metric ton, EURO6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 7.5-16 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	transport (batteries)
Industrial machine, heavy, unspecified {RER} industrial machine production, heavy, unspecified Cut-off, U	machines
Electricity, low voltage {CZ} market for electricity, low voltage Cut-off, U	Czech energy mix 2023
Diesel, low-sulfur {RER} market group for diesel, low-sulfur Cut-off, U	supply for crushing machine
Transport, freight, light commercial vehicle {Europe without Switzerland} market for transport, freight, light commercial vehicle Cut-off, U	transport (fire extinguisher, AC)
Transport, freight, lorry 3.5-7.5 metric ton, EURO6 {RER} transport, freight, lorry 3.5-7.5 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, U	transport (inverter)

Table 2. Ecoinvent 3.9 processes used for life cycle assessment modelling, used abbreviations: RoW = rest of the world, GLO = global, RER = rest of Europe.

The environmental impact categories (ICs) often vary based on the study's context and objectives but commonly include climate change, resource depletion, water pollution, air pollution, ecotoxicity, land use, and waste generation (Fazio et al., 2019). In this study, three primary ICs were identified: climate change, eutrophication, freshwater, and resource use,

minerals and metals. These were chosen for their industry relevance and significant normalized results across all BESS parts.

The climate change impacts were evaluated using the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) characterization model, which calculates the Global Warming Potential over 100 years (GWP100) in kilograms of carbon dioxide equivalent per kilogram (kg CO₂ eq.) of emission. The GWP data, relevant to emissions to air, were distributed across various emission compartments to align with ILCD and EF frameworks. Eutrophication, freshwater IC measures nutrient enrichment in freshwater ecosystems, primarily from phosphorus emissions, leading to eutrophication. This impact is significant due to the role of phosphorus as a limiting factor in freshwater environments expressed in phosphorus equivalents (kg P eq.). Resource use, minerals, and metals IC focus on consuming natural non-fossil resources, evaluating the extraction impact using the Abiotic Depletion Factor (ADF), expressed in kilograms of antimony equivalents (Sb eq.). This considers reserve concentrations and depletion rates with global applicability (Fazio et al., 2019).

2.3 Economic analysis

When the BESS reaches the EOL phase, treatment can offer numerous advantages. The most significant benefit is its positive environmental impacts, as it promotes the circular economy and reduces the generation of non-recyclable waste. Furthermore, recycling enables using recycled materials instead of relying solely on extracting primary raw materials. While the environmental benefits of recycling are evident, it is crucial for the process also to be economically feasible. The cost and quality of recycled raw materials should be on par with or superior to those obtained from primary raw materials through mining (Beaudet et al., 2020; Pražanová et al., 2022a).

From an economic perspective, the recycling of BESS can be evaluated based on the potential returns derived from the value and quantity of recycled materials and the costs involved in the recycling and recovery processes. Revenue generation hinges on the market price of recycled raw materials, with certain metals such as aluminium, cobalt, copper, and nickel holding substantial value, particularly in LIBs. On the cost front, expenses can be categorized into four groups, encompassing transportation costs for conveying BESS and its components for recycling, machine costs indicative of the price of pre-owned machinery, labour costs, and energy consumption-related expenses (Liao et al., 2019; Pražanová et al., 2022b; Sun et al., 2020).

In the context of this research, revenues were analysed, considering the valuation of partial raw material outputs based on prevailing market prices of the corresponding commodities. The average market price of the given commodity from 1/1/2024 to 10/7/2024 was predominantly utilized to assess most materials. However, due to the unavailability of historical pricing data for certain raw materials, current prices as of 10/7/2024 were employed for graphite and manganese. The valuation of steel and brass was aligned with the pricing of the relevant metal scrap, while the valuation of iron was tethered to the pricing of pig iron. Insight to used prices is provided in detail in Supplementary materials.

This study used a 100% efficient baseline scenario to define target conditions, which were recognized as idealized rather than realistic. Therefore, overall equipment effectiveness (OEE) was then factored into account for real-world conditions, acknowledging that machines will operate below full functionality due to micro downtimes and intermediate steps. This approach ensures that the analysis reflects realistic industrial scenarios.

For the analysis, costs were primarily determined by evaluating machine costs. This involved estimating the equipment's useful life (10 years), applying a 5% interest rate per year, and assuming 260 work shifts per year with 8-hour shifts. The purchase price and these assumptions were used to calculate the annual annuity payment, which was then divided by the

number of shifts per year to determine the machine cost per shift, accounting for the time value of money. Additionally, the EOL treatment for the primary component of the BESS, specifically the batteries, was thoroughly assessed, considering the duration of the cycle and the number of shifts required for its completion. Total machine costs were subsequently determined by multiplying the cost per shift by the number of shifts of the bottleneck machine, adjusted for its OEE. Furthermore, energy consumption for the entire BESS recycling process was estimated for the machinery and equipment used. The energy cost was derived by summing specific costs directly associated with electricity consumption, supplemented by fixed costs based on prevailing energy prices in the Czech Republic, budgeted for the relevant number of shifts.

The labour costs were calculated based on several factors, including the number of workers directly engaged in recycling, machine operation, and disassembling BESS and its sub-parts, as well as the appropriate number of shifts and the hourly wages for each employee. These cost calculations were based on the prevailing wages in blue-collar professions in the Czech Republic. Additionally, the expenses of transporting the BESS and its components were determined based on the distance travelled and the current per-kilometer transportation rates within the Czech Republic.

The total costs were calculated by aggregating machine, labour, transportation, and energy costs. This simplified approach attempts to account for the time value of money and the uninterrupted operation of machinery in the industrial process. Upon assessing the weight yield of the recycled materials and their market price, as well as the direct costs associated with their recycling, the potential earnings before interest and taxes (EBIT) were calculated. Then, the Czech Republic's VAT of 21% was applied to determine the tax burden, resulting in the net profit (EAT).

3. Results and discussion

In this study, the economic analysis was closely linked with the LCA inputs, using the EOL BESS treatment as a shared basis for both evaluations. This integrated approach allowed for a nuanced analysis, offering a holistic view of the economic implications of sustainability and environmental impact.

3.1 Environmental impact characterization

Within the scope of the provided LCA study, the focus was set on three specific ICs: climate change, eutrophication, freshwater; and resource use, minerals and metals. According to the obtained results, the most significant environmental benefits of BESS EOL treatment are primarily due to the reuse of secondary materials such as aluminium, copper, and steel, which can be effectively recycled and repurposed, extending their lifecycle.

The environmental impacts of the treated components were categorized into battery system, cooling system, fire extinguishing system, and inverters, as depicted in Figure 3. Results show significant environmental benefits from recycling and recycling pre-treatment, particularly due to the secondary use of materials like aluminium, steel/iron, copper, and graphite. Consistent with our findings, Kallitsis et al. (2022) reported that secondary aluminium contributes roughly 50% of the environmental benefits in battery recycling. Conversely, secondary steel offers minimal benefits, underscoring the greater environmental advantage of using secondary aluminium in sustainable recycling practices. These benefits outweigh the environmental impacts of transporting recycled materials, using electricity and machinery for recycling, and disposing of non-recycled materials such as waste plastic, electronic scrap, and refrigerant.

The most significant environmental benefits in the climate change IC come from recovering secondary aluminium from batteries, cooling systems, and inverters. In contrast, the benefits of fire extinguisher recycling are mainly due to the recovery of secondary steel.

Overall, the environmental benefits outweigh the associated impacts, which mostly stem from the electricity consumption of the machinery and sets, totalling approximately $1.2 \cdot 10^4$ kg CO₂ eq. The benefits are substantial, with a reduction of approximately $-2.54 \cdot 10^4$ kg CO₂ eq. However, it is essential to note that the environmental impacts of recycling pre-treatment processes for batteries accounts for about one-third of these environmental benefits. Compared to the study by Romare & Dahllöf (2017), which examined various battery recycling pathways, our results show more minor environmental benefits: i.e. $-1,023$ kg CO₂ eq./1 kg batteries versus $-1,536$ kg CO₂ eq./1 kg batteries in their study. This discrepancy is due to the Swedish energy mix used in their research, which has significantly lower carbon emissions than the Czech energy mix used in our study. Considering the analysis of the whole BESS unit, the environmental impacts from electricity used in battery recycling account for nearly one-third of the absolute value of the eutrophication, freshwater IC. The energy used to recycle other BESS components is minimal, in comparison. Significant environmental benefits arise from recovering secondary materials, particularly copper from batteries and AC units, steel from fire extinguishers, and aluminium from inverters. The main environmental benefits in this category come from the batteries (-25.36 kg P eq.) and inverter parts (-18.53 kg P eq.). Fire extinguishers contribute negligibly. The AC unit contribution is around 4.91 kg P eq. The environmental impact of the recycling process is minimal regarding resource use, minerals, and metals IC. However, significant benefits arise from recovering secondary metals such as copper, brass, steel, and aluminium. Batteries contribute the most to resource use, minerals, and metals IC, mainly due to the recovery of secondary copper, accounting for -4.68 kg Sb eq. The recycling of AC units follows, while the other components combined contribute -0.73 kg Sb eq.

In conclusion, enhancing EOL treatment efficiency and managing resources can improve the environmental benefits of EOL BESS treatment. The Czech Republic's energy sector heavily relies on fossil fuels, particularly coal, which exacerbates impacts. Reducing this reliance and transitioning to renewable energy would improve recycling outcomes and support broader sustainability goals. This analysis highlights the vital role of EOL treatment in reusing materials. By recovering aluminium, copper, and steel, recycling extends material lifecycles, reduces virgin material demand, conserves resources, and lowers carbon footprints. Ultimately, the environmental benefits of recycling far exceed its impacts, highlighting its essential role in sustainable resource management and environmental protection.

Figure 3. Studied environmental category (climate change, eutrophication, freshwater, resource use, minerals, and metals) results for end-of-life treatment of (a) battery system, (b) cooling system, (c) extinguishing system, and (d) inverters. Numerical data supporting the provided results are included in the Supplementary materials.

3.2 Economic viability analysis

The economic analysis results depend on the revenues from recycled materials and recycling costs. Material recovery relies on process efficiency and material inputs based on cathode composition and battery design. The process influences machinery, labour, energy, and transport costs, with potential tax obligations varying by state. This study focused on NMC 6.5:2:1.5 LIB pouch cells, achieving 100% recovery efficiency for metals and graphite in the baseline scenario and different OEE levels covering the operation conditions. Recovered materials include aluminium, brass, cobalt, copper, iron, graphite, manganese, nickel, and steel, with cobalt, nickel, and copper being the most valuable.

Considering the market prices and weights of recycled materials, the analysis reveals that nickel comprises the largest share of potential profits, exceeding 50%. Cobalt follows, trailed by aluminium and copper, constituting more than 90% of the potential profits, as shown in Figure 4 (a). It is essential to highlight the significance of graphite, which represents approximately 6% of the potential profits. However, the strategic importance of graphite lies in the potential for local acquisition because over 60% of graphite is mined in China (Government of Canada, 2024; Statista, 2023). This concern is heightened by the concentration of refining facilities in China, creating dependence on Chinese supplies and vulnerability to their influence. Similarly, the concentration of cobalt in the Democratic Republic of Congo, which produces over half of the global supply, raises concerns about supply chain resilience and geopolitical influence due to heavy reliance on a single source.

The analysis in Figure 4 (b) compares potential revenues, costs, and taxation, highlighting energy and labour as major cost drivers. The study indicates machine costs are relatively low, due to the study's focus on specific processes, excluding broader technological support. The cost analysis is based on the EOL treatment of one BESS, with fixed costs tied to work shifts and assuming full-capacity operation. Deviations from total capacity will increase per-BESS recycling costs.

In this case study, assuming 100% efficiency in metal and graphite recovery and an 85% OEE, potential revenues are projected to be €105,000. With current prices for recycled materials, estimated costs are €36,000, including about half for taxes. Thus, recycling BESS under these conditions could yield a profit of around €69,000. The influence of OEE and potential imperfections in the recycling process, which reduces the efficiency of recovering valuable materials from the black mass, is graphically depicted in Figure 4 (c). A decrease in OEE leads to higher costs, while lower recycling efficiency reduces potential revenues. Additionally, as revenues decline and costs rise, potential tax obligations decrease slightly, partially offsetting the negative impact on projected profits.

This focused BESS economic analysis highlights the clear financial benefits of recycling. There is substantial potential to offset the costs of integrating additional technologies and processes into the recycling operation. While profits may decrease when these extra costs are considered, profitability remains promising in the context of EOL treatment. Additionally, local production of raw materials can reduce import reliance, enhance supply chain security, and lower costs and environmental impacts associated with transporting materials from abroad.

Figure 4. Economic analysis results of end-of-life treatment of battery energy storage system: (a) value of individual materials of system components, (b) revenues and costs analysis, (c) illustration of profits vs. black mass loss for different overall equipment effectiveness levels.

4. Conclusion

This study evaluated the environmental and economic impacts of EOL treatment for BESS based on LIBs. Focusing on a 2.8 MWh/2.5 MW BESS, the study covers the recycling pre-treatment of batteries, recycling treatment of cooling systems, extinguishing systems, inverters, and the reuse of containers and substations in new BESS installations. The environmental assessment employs a gate-to-gate LCA to measure impacts on three critical ICs: climate change, freshwater eutrophication, and resource use, minerals and metals.

The results indicate significant environmental benefits derived from recycling and pre-treatment processes, primarily due to the secondary use of materials like aluminium, copper, and steel. Notably, secondary aluminium contributes approximately 50% of the environmental benefits in battery recycling, while secondary steel offers minimal advantages. The most significant environmental benefits in the climate change IC arise from recovering secondary aluminium from batteries, cooling systems, and inverters. In contrast, the recycling of fire extinguishers mainly yields benefits from secondary steel recovery. Overall, the environmental advantages of recycling outweigh the environmental impacts associated with the electricity consumption of the machinery used, which totals approximately $1.2 \cdot 10^4$ kg CO₂ eq. The environmental impacts of recycling pre-treatment processes for batteries accounts for about one-third of the observed benefits.

In terms of economic analysis, the study reveals that nickel comprises the largest share of potential profits, exceeding 50%, followed by cobalt, aluminium, and copper, which collectively constitute more than 90% of potential profits. The analysis further emphasizes the strategic importance of graphite, which represents approximately 6% of potential profits but is also critically dependent on local sourcing due to its predominant production in China. The study's findings underscore the potential value of BESS containers at EOL, which can significantly influence investment decisions by offsetting market risks. The documented return from EOL processing of BESS containers can lower investment risks and foster a transition to greener energy. Local production of raw materials further enhances economic benefits by reducing import reliance, improving supply chain security, and lowering costs.

Though based in the Czech Republic, the methodology is applicable globally. In summary, BESS recycling offers triple benefits: environmental improvement through material reuse, reducing reliance on import, and economic gains from local production. Transitioning to renewable energy sources for recycling would further optimize these benefits, aligning with sustainability objectives and ensuring a more efficient and eco-friendly approach to BESS EOL treatment.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Anna Pražanová: Resources, Methodology, Conceptualization, Writing – Original draft, Project administration.

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David Havlíček: Resources, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Jan Weinzettel: Supervision, Writing – Review & Editing.

Daniel-Ioan Stroe: Supervision, Writing – Review & Editing.

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Declaration of competing interest

All authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Acknowledgement

This work was financially supported by the Czech Science Foundation, grant No. 23-07984X, and the Grant Agency of the CTU in Prague, grant No. SGS24/136/OHK3/3T/13. Additionally, the infrastructure used was made available through the project "The Energy Conversion and Storage", funded as project No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004617 by Programme Johannes Amos Comenius, call Excellent Research.

Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at XXX.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the authors used ChatGPT in order to improve readability and language. After using this tool/service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

References

- Beaudet, A., Larouche, F., Amouzegar, K., Bouchard, P., & Zaghbi, K. (2020). Key Challenges and Opportunities for Recycling Electric Vehicle Battery Materials. *Sustainability* 2020, Vol. 12, Page 5837, 12(14), 5837. <https://doi.org/10.3390/SU12145837>
- Bobba, S., Mathieux, F., Ardente, F., Blengini, G. A., Cusenza, M. A., Podias, A., & Pfrang, A. (2018). Life Cycle Assessment of repurposed electric vehicle batteries: an adapted method based on modelling energy flows. *Journal of Energy Storage*, 19, 213–225. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2018.07.008>
- Chang, Y. C., Chang, H. C., & Huang, C. Y. (2018). Design and Implementation of the Battery Energy Storage System in DC Micro-Grid Systems. *Energies* 2018, Vol. 11, Page 1566, 11(6), 1566. <https://doi.org/10.3390/EN11061566>
- Chen, M., Ma, X., Chen, B., Arsenault, R., Karlson, P., Simon, N., & Wang, Y. (2019). Recycling End-of-Life Electric Vehicle Lithium-Ion Batteries. *Joule*, 3(11), 2622–2646. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JOULE.2019.09.014>
- Conzen, J., Lakshmipathy, S., Kapahi, A., Kraft, S., & DiDomizio, M. (2023). Lithium ion battery energy storage systems (BESS) hazards. *Journal of Loss Prevention in the Process Industries*, 81, 104932. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JLP.2022.104932>
- Czech electricity and gas market operator (OTE a.s.). (2024). *National Residual Mix, Czech Republic — English*. https://www.ote-cr.cz/en/statistics/national-residual-mix?set_language=en
- Divya, K. C., & Østergaard, J. (2009). Battery energy storage technology for power systems—An overview. *Electric Power Systems Research*, 79(4), 511–520. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.EPSR.2008.09.017>
- Fazio, S., Biganzoli, F., De, L. V., Zampori, L., Sala, S., & Diaconu, E. (2019). *Supporting information to the characterisation factors of recommended EF Life Cycle Impact Assessment methods*. <https://doi.org/10.2760/002447>

- Gaines, L. (2018). Lithium-ion battery recycling processes: Research towards a sustainable course. *Sustainable Materials and Technologies*, 17. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SUSMAT.2018.E00068>
- Global, F. (2017). *DS 5-33 Electrical Energy Storage Systems (Data Sheet)*.
- Government of Canada, N. R. C. (2024). *Graphite facts*. <https://natural-resources.canada.ca/our-natural-resources/minerals-mining/mining-data-statistics-and-analysis/minerals-metals-facts/graphite-facts/24027>
- Hannan, M. A., Wali, S. B., Ker, P. J., Rahman, M. S. A., Mansor, M., Ramachandaramurthy, V. K., Muttaqi, K. M., Mahlia, T. M. I., & Dong, Z. Y. (2021). Battery energy-storage system: A review of technologies, optimization objectives, constraints, approaches, and outstanding issues. *Journal of Energy Storage*, 42, 103023. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.EST.2021.103023>
- Havlíček, D. (2024). *Assessment of environmental and economic aspects of waste treatment of lithium-ion battery energy storage*. Czech Technical University in Prague.
- Hayes, S. M., & McCullough, E. A. (2018). Critical minerals: A review of elemental trends in comprehensive criticality studies. *Resources Policy*, 59, 192–199. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.RESOURPOL.2018.06.015>
- HIVE Connective Intelligence. (2023). *Introduction to Battery Energy Storage System (BESS)*.
- Hossain, E., Murtaugh, D., Mody, J., Faruque, H. M. R., Sunny, M. S. H., & Mohammad, N. (2019). A Comprehensive Review on Second-Life Batteries: Current State, Manufacturing Considerations, Applications, Impacts, Barriers Potential Solutions, Business Strategies, and Policies. *IEEE Access*, 7, 73215–73252. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2917859>
- IBG Česko s.r.o. (2019). *High-capacity battery system*. <https://www.ibg.cz/en/reference/high-capacity-battery-system>
- Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). (2023). Climate Change 2021 – The Physical Science Basis. *Climate Change 2021 – The Physical Science Basis*. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009157896>
- International Organization for Standardization. (2006). *ISO 14040:2006 - Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Principles and framework*. 2 Edition. <https://www.iso.org/standard/37456.html>
- IRENA. (2017). Electricity storage and renewables: Costs and markets to 2030. *International Renewable Energy Agency, October*, 132. https://www.irena.org/-/media/Files/IRENA/Agency/Publication/2017/Oct/IRENA_Electricity_Storage_Costs_2017.pdf
- IRENA. (2023). Innovation landscape for smart electrification: Decarbonising end-use sectors with renewable power. *International Renewable Energy Agency, Abu Dhabi*. www.irena.org
- Jasper, F. B., Späthe, J., Baumann, M., Peters, J. F., Ruhland, J., & Weil, M. (2022). Life cycle assessment (LCA) of a battery home storage system based on primary data. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 366, 132899. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JCLEPRO.2022.132899>
- Kallitsis, E., Korre, A., & Kelsall, G. H. (2022). Life cycle assessment of recycling options for automotive Li-ion battery packs. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 371, 133636. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JCLEPRO.2022.133636>
- Larcher, D., & Tarascon, J. M. (2015). Towards greener and more sustainable batteries for electrical energy storage. *Nature Chemistry*, 7(1), 19–29. <https://doi.org/10.1038/NCHEM.2085>
- Li, L., Zhang, X., Li, M., Chen, R., Wu, F., Amine, K., & Lu, J. (2018). The Recycling of

- Spent Lithium-Ion Batteries: a Review of Current Processes and Technologies. *Electrochemical Energy Reviews*, 1(4), 461–482. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S41918-018-0012-1>
- Li Li, Zhang Xiaoxiao, Li Matthew, Chen Renjie, Wu Feng, Amine Khalil, & Lu Jun. (2018). *The Recycling of Spent Lithium-Ion Batteries: a Review of Current Processes and Technologies*. *Electrochemical Energy Reviews*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41918-018-0012-1>
- Liao, Q., Zhang, Y., Tao, Y., Ye, J., & Li, C. (2019). Economic analysis of an industrial photovoltaic system coupling with battery storage. *International Journal of Energy Research*, 43(12), 6461–6474. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ER.4482>
- Liu, S., Ma, T., Wang, F., Bai, G., Wei, Z., Wei, M., Li, Y., Lin, C., & Hu, J. (2022). Influence of Deep-Discharge Rate on Recycle Process of High Energy Density Traction Batteries. *Journal of Electrochemical Energy Conversion and Storage*, 19(2). <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.4052628>
- Megarevo. (2024). *MEGA Series Power Conversion System (without Transformer)*. <http://solars-inverter.com/3-2-power-conversion-system.html>
- Natarajan, S., & Aravindan, V. (2018). Recycling Strategies for Spent Li-Ion Battery Mixed Cathodes. *ACS Energy Letters*, 3(9), 2101–2103. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ACSENERGYLETT.8B01233>
- Nebey, A. H. (2024). Recent advancement in demand side energy management system for optimal energy utilization. *Energy Reports*, 11, 5422–5435. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.EGYR.2024.05.028>
- Ohrelius, M., Berg, M., Wreland Lindström, R., & Lindbergh, G. (2023). Lifetime Limitations in Multi-Service Battery Energy Storage Systems. *Energies* 2023, Vol. 16, Page 3003, 16(7), 3003. <https://doi.org/10.3390/EN16073003>
- Ovaskainen, M., Paakkunainen, T., Barcón, S., Barcón, P. Q., & City, M. (2023). Main characteristics to consider in a BESS during the design process. *IEEE International Autumn Meeting on Power, Electronics and Computing (ROPEC 2023)*.
- Pinto, G. X. A., Napolini, H. F., & Rüther, R. (2024). Assessing the economic viability of BESS in distributed PV generation on public buildings in Brazil: A 2030 outlook. *Renewable Energy*, 225, 120252. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.RENENE.2024.120252>
- Prakash, K., Ali, M., Siddique, M. N. I., Chand, A. A., Kumar, N. M., Dong, D., & Pota, H. R. (2022). A review of battery energy storage systems for ancillary services in distribution grids: Current status, challenges and future directions. *Frontiers in Energy Research*, 10, 971704. <https://doi.org/10.3389/FENRG.2022.971704/BIBTEX>
- Pražanová, A., Míka, M. H., & Knap, V. (2022). Lithium-ion battery module-to-cell: disassembly and material analysis. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 2382(1), 012002. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/2382/1/012002>
- Pražanová, Anna, Knap, V., & Stroe, D.-I. (2022a). Literature Review, Recycling of Lithium-Ion Batteries from Electric Vehicles, Part I: Recycling Technology. *Energies* 2022, Vol. 15, Page 1086, 15(3), 1086. <https://doi.org/10.3390/EN15031086>
- Pražanová, Anna, Knap, V., & Stroe, D.-I. (2022b). Literature Review, Recycling of Lithium-Ion Batteries from Electric Vehicles, Part II: Environmental and Economic Perspective. *Energies* 2022, Vol. 15, Page 7356, 15(19), 7356. <https://doi.org/10.3390/EN15197356>
- Romare, M., & Dahllöf, L. (2017). *The Life Cycle Energy Consumption and Greenhouse Gas Emissions from Lithium-Ion Batteries A Study with Focus on Current Technology and Batteries for light-duty vehicles*. www.ivl.se
- Salim, H. K., Stewart, R. A., Sahin, O., & Dudley, M. (2020). Systems approach to end-of-life management of residential photovoltaic panels and battery energy storage system in Australia. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 134, 110176.

- <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.RSER.2020.110176>
- Salim, Hengky K., Stewart, R. A., Sahin, O., & Dudley, M. (2019). Drivers, barriers and enablers to end-of-life management of solar photovoltaic and battery energy storage systems: A systematic literature review. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 211, 537–554. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JCLEPRO.2018.11.229>
- Selvamathi, R., Indragandhi, V., & AshokKumar, L. (2018). Analysis of transformer less inverter for PV applications. *International Journal of Engineering & Technology*, 7(2), 427–432. <https://doi.org/10.14419/IJET.V7I2.9995>
- Siemens s.r.o. (2019). *C-energy s.r.o. Teplárna Planá Nad Lužnicí, Bateriové Úložiště*, . <https://www.c-energy.cz/energeticky-zdroj-c-energy-plana-uvadi-do-provozu-nejvetsi-bateriove-uloziste-v-cr-dodane-firmou-siemens>
- Sommerville, R., Zhu, P., Rajaeifar, M. A., Heidrich, O., Goodship, V., & Kendrick, E. (2021). A qualitative assessment of lithium ion battery recycling processes. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 165. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.RESCONREC.2020.105219>
- Statista. (2023). *Global graphite production by country 2023*. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/267366/world-graphite-production/>
- Suleman, S. J. (2023). *Lifecycle Assessment of a Lithium-ion Battery Storage System for Frequency Regulation in a Real-World Application*.
- Sun, B., Su, X., Wang, D., Zhang, L., Liu, Y., Yang, Y., Liang, H., Gong, M., Zhang, W., & Jiang, J. (2020). Economic analysis of lithium-ion batteries recycled from electric vehicles for secondary use in power load peak shaving in China. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 276. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JCLEPRO.2020.123327>
- Thompson, D. L., Hartley, J. M., Lambert, S. M., Shiref, M., Harper, G. D. J., Kendrick, E., Anderson, P., Ryder, K. S., Gaines, L., & Abbott, A. P. (2020). The importance of design in lithium ion battery recycling—a critical review †. *Green Chemistry*, 22(7585). <https://doi.org/10.1039/d0gc02745f>
- Toro, L., Moscardini, E., Baldassari, L., Forte, F., Falcone, I., Coletta, J., & Toro, L. (2023). A Systematic Review of Battery Recycling Technologies: Advances, Challenges, and Future Prospects. *Energies* 2023, Vol. 16, Page 6571, 16(18), 6571. <https://doi.org/10.3390/EN16186571>
- Wang, X., Gaustad, G., Babbitt, C. W., & Richa, K. (2014). Economies of scale for future lithium-ion battery recycling infrastructure. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 83, 53–62. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2013.11.009>
- Zakeri, B., & Syri, S. (2015). Electrical energy storage systems: A comparative life cycle cost analysis. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 42, 569–596. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.RSER.2014.10.011>
- Zhu, P., Gastol, D., Marshall, J., Sommerville, R., Goodship, V., & Kendrick, E. (2021). A review of current collectors for lithium-ion batteries. *Journal of Power Sources*, 485, 229321. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JPOWSOUR.2020.229321>